
Peralkaline and alkaline magmatism of the Ossa-Morena Zone, SW Iberia: age, sources and implications for the Paleozoic evolution of Gondwanan lithosphere

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The Ossa-Morena Zone in SW Iberia represents a section of the northern margin of West Gondwana that retains a record of rifting that led to opening of the Rheic Ocean in the early Paleozoic. We present U-Pb zircon data from three alkaline to peralkaline syenites intruding Neoproterozoic and Cambrian strata that give crystallization ages ranging between the Upper Cambrian (Furongian) and Early Ordovician (Floian). Lu/Hf isotopic data from the zircons give positive initial ϵ_{Hf} values that approach model values for the depleted mantle at the time of crystallization, thus suggesting a significant mantle-derived component and limited mixing/assimilation with crust-derived melts. Alkaline/peralkaline magmatic suites of similar age and chemical composition intruded other sections of the northern margin of West Gondwana. This type of magmatism is traceable along the boundaries of the continental blocks constituting Iberia, which are also characterized by the presence of metamorphic belts with high-pressure rocks formed during the accretion and subsequent collision of peri-Gondwanan domains against Laurussia. Our U-Pb and Lu-Hf datasets indicate that during the Cambrian–Ordovician transition, lithospheric extension reached a stage of narrow intra-continental rifting where deeply-sourced magmas, probably coming from the lower crust and/or the upper mantle, intruded continental upper crust across various sections of the previously stretched crust. We propose that multiple necking of the Gondwana lithosphere led to compartmentalization of extensional activity (multi-block model), favouring the onset of early Paleozoic peralkaline and alkaline magmas. The structure of this broad area of thinned lithosphere underlain by fertile mantle, eventually consisted of several continental micro-blocks. The boundaries of the micro-blocks were zones of inherited crustal weakness that were subsequently reactivated during the Late Paleozoic as major accretionary faults related to the amalgamation of Pangaea during the Variscan orogeny.